

CARIES CLASSES

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Abstract: in this article we will consider the classes and types of caries

Key words: Caries, Types of caries, Classes.

Caries is the most common dental disease. It affects the hard tissues of the tooth, develops gradually, leads to the formation of a cavity and the destruction of the crown. Several classifications are used for this disease, including the developed one.

It distinguishes several types of caries by location and course:

enamel: affects only surface tissues, changes their structure, which is why the enamel surface can become matte, lighten or darken, look like a chalk stain. This is the initial stage of the disease, in which hard tissues begin to break down against the background of demineralization;

dentine: the lesion penetrates into deeper layers, but does not go beyond the dentine layer. A recess with a light or dark bottom is formed in hard tissues;

cement: the lesion affects the root of the tooth, may develop in the cervical part of the crown. It is dangerous for the rapid spread of infection and the destruction of hard tissues;

suspended: with such caries, the condition of the destroyed, affected tissues stabilizes, and the process does not develop for some time, the area of carious lesion does not increase. The disease "stops" only for a while (up to several weeks), after which the tooth destruction continues.

Classes of caries according to Black:

Grade 1 – it is characterized by lesions of depressions, grooves and dimples on the upper part of the chewing teeth (molars, premolars), canines and incisors. This problem may affect only part or the entire occlusal plane;

2nd grade, that is, the development of pathology in the contact space between the teeth. Most often, a similar problem occurs on the molars and premolars, on the distal and medial surfaces. It can affect the dental crown in several places at once. This type of dental disease is difficult to notice, so it can develop into serious damage. It is possible to identify a disease of the 2nd class only at a dental examination or with the help of CT;

Grade 3 – the development of caries between the front teeth (incisors and canines). Defective foci occur in the interdental space (medial and distal zones),

without affecting the upper part of the crown. The defeat can be noticed independently. It looks like a small dark spot between the teeth;

Class 4 – carious process of the lateral surface, including the cutting ridge. Usually the pathology develops on the front teeth;

5th grade is a destructive process affecting the cervical region. It develops on the lingual and vestibular surfaces. Pathology can destroy all types of teeth.

The 6th grade of caries. This category includes the formation of carious foci on the cutting edges of molars, premolars, incisors and canines. The pathological process develops only at the upper edge.

The Black classification includes different types of carious lesions. According to the depth, pathology is divided into initial, superficial, medium and deep degrees:

At the initial stage, spots of a light or darkish hue appear. After their removal, remineralization is applied.

The superficial degree is characterized by enamel damage, roughness and hypersensitivity to sour, sweet, salty, spicy, warm and cold. The treatment consists in grinding the dental surface and remineralization. Sometimes a carious lesion is treated and a seal is installed.

In the middle stage, the enamel is destroyed down to the dentin. The process is accompanied by sharp pain. The doctor removes the carious tissue and performs a filling.

The deep degree affects the enamel and dentin. With untimely treatment, the pathology can develop into periodontitis or pulpitis.

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